

Church of Panagia (Our Lady) Angeloktisti, Kition

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Christian Traditions, Orthodox/Eastern Christian, Religious Place, Orthodoxy, Orthodoxy, Cyprus, Kition, Larnaca

The church of Panagia Angeloktisti (meaning “built by angels” in Greek) was erected in the village of Kiti in Cyprus. According to the foundation legend, the population of ancient Kition moved to the present village of Kiti for fleeing the Arab invasions. In their new dwelling they set about to build a church in honour of the Virgin. During the construction of the church, the foundations had moved to a different location overnight. After the occurrence of the miracle, they continued to build the church on the new site and returned every morning to find that work had progressed overnight in their absence. Many claimed to have seen an army of angels building the church and hence they proclaimed it “Angeloktisti”. Yet, almost nothing is known for certain about the early settlement of the village and the foundation of the church. The present structure was built in the 11th century, over the ruins of a 5th-century basilica that was destroyed most probably around the 7th or the 8th century. The columnar basilica had three aisles, an eastern apse, lateral apsidioles, and a wooden roof. It combined a variety of decorative elements, including an apse mosaic, marble revetments, and stucco relief. The exposed stucco on the east wall suggests that the mosaic was always confined to the space of the apse conch. The apse with the semi-circular synthronon and the famous mosaic depicting the Virgin of the earlier basilica was incorporated into the domed cross-in-square 11th-century structure. The current form of the church is a result of later additions and alterations. In the 12th century, a barrel-vaulted chapel dedicated to saints Kosmas and Damianos was added to the north. Between the end of the 13th century and the beginning of the 14th century, another chapel –the so-called Latin chapel– was built to the south for the needs of the Catholic population. The three coats-of-arms that still survive above the Latin chapel’s entrance belong to the Frankish family Gibelet, who have been the patrons of the chapel. The presence in the chapel of the tombstone of Simone Renier de Gibelet, who died in 1302 confirms this. It furthermore suggests that the chapel may have had a funerary character. The mosaic in the conch of the apse is considered one of the most significant and elaborate mosaics of the Early Christian period. It was likely created in the 6th century. It depicts the Virgin standing on a stool, holding Christ in her left arm, against a golden background. On the Virgin’s right is Archangel Michael and on her left is Archangel Gabriel. The Archangels hold a sceptre and offer a globe with a cross to the Virgin and Child. The mosaic is the oldest, surviving monumental representation of the standing Virgin holding the Child with her left arm. On the inscription she is referred to as “Η ΑΓΙΑ ΜΑΡΙΑ” (“Holy Mary”) instead of Theotokos (“Mother of God”). Hence, the inscription is intriguing, since the Virgin is named thus only in the Monophysite districts of Anatolia. The mosaic is surrounded by a border that depicts a total of six fountains flanked by pairs of confronted or addorsed animals (stags) or birds (ducks, parrots). The mosaic has two decorative borders. At the base of the mosaic the border is wide with geometric and floral decoration. Beneath the lower border is a narrow border with a crowstep pattern in red and white. The apse mosaic was framed by stucco decoration. The church was decorated with wall-paintings in the 13th century which were uncovered in the main church and the north chapel. Fragments of paintings from the 14th, and 15th to 16th centuries also survive, with overpainting ascribed to the 18th century. The church is furnished with a wooden iconostasis of the 16th century. The Church of Panagia Angeloktisti was submitted as a possible UNESCO World Heritage Site in September 2015 and is currently listed on the Tentative list of UNESCO World Heritage Sites.

Date Range: 400 CE - 1500 CE

Region: Church of Panagia Angeloktisti

Region tags: Cyprus, Kition, Larnaca

Church of Panagia (Our Lady) Angeloktisti

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Religious Specialists
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Foulías, A. The Church of Our Lady Angeloktisti at Kiti: A Visitor's Guide. Nicosia, 2012
- Source 2: Papageorgiou, A. "To Kition Kata Thn Vyzantinín Kai Mesaionikín Períodon." *Kypriakáí Spoudai* 62–63 (2000): 199–209
- Source 3: Nicolaou, K. The Historical Topography of Kition. Göteborg, 1976

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/tentativelists/5987/>
- Source 1 Description: Unesco World Heritage Sites Tentative list
- Source 1 URL: <https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/mosaic-of-panagia-tis-angeloktisti-kiti-cyprus-ce197a42cd1348798b832cec2c8c0de5>
- Source 1 Description: 3D model of the mosaic of the apse of Panagia Angeloktisti

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1950-2010

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavations were undertaken by the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Other [specify]: It is not associated at all with landscape features

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Other [specify]: Domed cross-in-square structure

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: The church is not made of a single feature

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

Notes: The apse of the basilica was integrated into the Byzantine church. Two chapels were added: the first in the 12th century and the second in the end of the 13th or the beginning of the 14th century.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

Notes: The present structure was not destroyed. However, parts of the present construction belong to an earlier 5th-century structure which was destroyed.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The Church is dedicated to the Virgin, the Mother of God.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: The church was built by the residents of ancient Kition who have moved at the present area for fleeing the Arab raids.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– No

Notes: The main construction does not include the use of wood. However, the furnishing of the church like the iconostasis, the icons, the proskynetaria that hold the icons and the seats are made of wood.

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pigments and binders were used for the frescoes. Glass tesserae were used for the mosaic of the apse.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: The tesserae of the mosaic of the apse are human-made.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: The church is furnished with a 16th-century iconostasis on which are hanged important icons.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

Notes: The Son of God is depicted.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints and the Mother of God.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The border of the mosaic of the apse included animals and birds

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

Notes: The decoration is figural. However, the border of the mosaic with the Virgin is non-figural.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Notes: The mosaic with the Virgin was not hidden purposefully. However, the iconostasis limits the access to it.

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

– Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: The only scene that has survived is that of the Annunciation.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The state of the painted decoration of the church is fragmentary and therefore we cannot know what the cycle included initially.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The border of the mosaic with the Virgin and the Child included animals and birds that have symbolic meaning.

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

Notes: There are mosaics but they do not have a decorative role. They have a functional role, since they mention the name of the saints and the scenes depicted. There is also a dedicatory inscription in the nave, next to the depiction of saint John the Baptist.

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: Following byzantine tradition.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Archangels are depicted flanking the Virgin.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: Crosses.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Apart from the Virgin with the Child flanked by angels of the mosaic decoration of the apse, in the church were depicted saints and biblical scenes.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Unfortunately the mosaic decoration and the painted decoration of the different phases have come down to us in a fragmentary state and so we cannot know more about the composition of the initial iconographic programme.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The church is not a burial. However, the excavations at the Latin chapel have proved that it must have been used as a place of burials.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: The Latin chapel of the church was used for burials.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Pilgrims are coming though to pray to God, Christ, the Virgin and the various saints.

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: Pilgrims are coming to the church to pray.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings to the church can vary from very precious objects to daily-life objects and aliments.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Material offerings to the church can vary from very precious objects to daily-life objects and aliments.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Material offerings to the church can vary from very precious objects to daily-

life objects and aliments.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: The monument is overlooked, preserved and restored by a team of specialists composed by conservators, priests, architects and chemists under the surveillance of the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus and the Church of Cyprus.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The monument is overlooked, preserved and restored by a team of specialists composed by conservators, priests, architects and chemists under the surveillance of the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus and the Church of Cyprus.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– No

Notes: The church celebrates though once a year and thus a large number of pilgrims is coming for the feast.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The Holy liturgy is celebrated there regularly. Services such as baptisms, funerals, weddings etc. are also taking place at the church.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Unknown

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Regularly

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The services follow the Greek Orthodox rite.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Notes: The services follow the Greek Orthodox rite.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– No

Notes: Priests are present at the church for the services and liturgies. The rest of the time the church is open for pilgrims and visitors.

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Notes: Priests are present at the church for the services and liturgies. The rest of the time the church is open for pilgrims and visitors.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: The Christian Orthodox priests are always male.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
– Yes

Notes: The Orthodox Church is organised hierarchically. The priests of the church belong to the lower classes of clergy.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Yes

Notes: Apart from the Church of Cyprus and the Holy Bishopric of Kition the church is maintained by the Department of Antiquities of Cyprus.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Notes: In the early twentieth century the Latin chapel was used as an elementary school.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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